

Sustainable Management practice in the Textile Industry: Empowering the designer through strategy

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Abstract: This study addresses sustainable practices within the textile industry, emphasizing the designer's role in influencing corporate strategies toward environmental goals. Given the United Nations' 2030 Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) approach, particularly Goal 12 on sustainable consumption, the study identifies key challenges designers face due to limitations in authority and strategic involvement. Using a grounded theory approach and case studies, we explore effective design-led strategies for circularity, focusing on sustainable materials selection and waste reduction in textile manufacturing. Emphasizing the potential for systemic change, this paper aims to empower designers within organizational structures to actively contribute to sustainable development.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Sustainable Textiles, Design Management.

1 Introduction

As the year 2030 rapidly approaches and the targets and goals of the United Nations Sustainability Development Goals (SDG) loom large on that horizon with Goal 12 Sustainable Consumption focussing on, amongst other things Chemical and Waste, the designer is faced with a lack of power or authority to intervene, a more positive position in this power circle would be beneficial to planet and profit.

With this paper, we hope to explore the function of clothing beyond the usual durability and serviceability and articulate a more articulate response to circularity and sustainability through materials selection and specification. Synthetic fabrics are a particular blocker in the pathway to circularity, with blended natural and synthetic filament a key concern.

In a recent speech [1] delivered by Ligia Noronha at the G7 Environment minister's sessions, out of 4 key areas of G7's environment action, Number 1 was 'plastics and number 3 'textiles and fashion' (alongside building and construction, and minerals and metals.)

With the “C” [Chief] Suite taken up traditionally with Business and Technology executives, only in very few instances has the Chief Design Officer had a seat at the strategy table. The designer sits within a department usually as subordinate to a STEM manager in an ‘inhouse’ design situation, the designer can be vocal on compliance in sustainability at their peril, with loss of employment a serious circumstance, even when citing legislation and worlds best practices.

With the advent of the concept of “purpose” in the triple bottom line operational framework, large corporations to small to medium enterprises grapple with Profit while existing with Planet, employing people to fulfill a function, purpose has emerged as the fourth “P” to frame the environment (planet) as the most significant element of manufacture causing a rethink on vision and mission.

While the designer has shown they can have input at all levels of the innovation ladder, management subjugates them to the level of stylist, only occasionally engaging them in process and minimally allowing them sanction in the strategic sanctuary of the C suite.

Textiles are in the frame for the major increase in microplastic pollution [2] in the world environment, with microplastic filaments exposed in the Himalayas retreating glaciers and found within the cells of heart muscle and brain across all species. [3].

So, we pose the question “How can the designer influence corporate direction in sustainable textile manufacture”?

This article will take a grounded theory approach to researching grey literature through a desktop literature review and include case study exemplars in environmental sustainability and organisational management to provide a firm global context for designers to establish impactful processes in building sustainable practices within the textile and clothing sector in developing nations.

With a particular focus on India and its extensive footprint in this industry, the paper hopes to provide direction in framing design for sustainability principles linked to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

With rapacious consumption in the textile and clothing sector, movements are being advanced to intervene, such as “sufficiency” [4] around human behaviour to lead change, which can be framed around the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)12 Target 12.8 to ‘Promote universal understanding of sustainable lifestyles’ [5]. Fast Fashion is a meme used across sectors to highlight this consumption excess. This approach reflects the economic movement around ‘Degrowth’ alongside slow fashion as a counter to the last two decades where growth has been supported through corrupt political manipulations [6].

More commonly developing nations such as China discuss “slow design” in an attempt to raise quality over quantity [7] but this report through the Institute of International Sustainable Development Limited (ISD) ‘Sustinari’ largely levels responsibility at the designer, while not recognising the tenuous situation that an ‘in house’ designer faces when relating world’s best practice to management, who effectively have the final say on selection of materials and budgets tied to contracts, especially in the ‘fast fashion’ world of fast moving consumer goods environments internationally to meet

SDG12 [5] target 12.6 to ‘encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices and sustainable reporting by the year 2030.

As design has broadly attained a firmer footing within the corporation’s innovation ladder, a rung above the ‘design as styling’ level and inputs into ‘design as process’, it is the final level that needs a focus in building a green and sustainable textile and clothing industry, [8] building on Anders Kretzschmar’s 2003 work and research through the Danish Design Centre.

What this paper hopes to achieve is a preliminary framing of guidelines to assist designers in strategy, at any level of practice as individual makers, inhouse or contract to foster best practices amongst the textile and clothing manufacturing industries, to guide the ‘C’ Suite towards better modes of operation to causally effect a shift in the use of synthetic blended filaments.

2 Fibres and Plastics in textiles

For the entire human history fibres from both animal and vegetable sources have been employed as apparel, shelter, functional goods as a sign of identity, and of course, status.

Perhaps none more significant than silk. To discover and replicate the process by which certain insects were able to extrude such a desirable fibre from their bodies was the impetus for the invention or synthesis of ‘artificial silk’ in the 1890’s.

Fig. 1. Eco-I manual p12 Textile Material Categorisation (note polypropylene animal-based additives)

Synthetic fibres have, since then, revolutionized every aspect of the fashion and textile industries for the filament's consistency in manufacture and production. These man-made materials have not only reshaped the way garments are produced but have also significantly influenced trends, consumer behaviour, and the very nature of fashion itself.

The search for a human-made silk was finally successful in 1878 when Hilaire Bernigaud, Count de Chardonnet, developed an artificial fibre that resembled the silk filament. In 1884 Bernigaud was granted a patent for his method which was based on extruding a solution of cellulose nitrate through fine glass capillaries.

The fibre was called RAYON and was exhibited at the Paris Exposition in 1889. Many other research chemists were developing similar processes so in 1891 Bernigaud opened a factory in Besancon 'Societe de la Soie de Chardonnet' (Society of the Silk of Chardonnet) to commercially produce the fibre that he called 'Chardonnet Silk'.

2.2 The Emergence of Synthetic Fibres

The journey of synthetic fibres continued in the 1930s with the invention of Nylon by chemist Wallace Carothers and his team at DuPont. Introduced to the public in 1939, nylon was marketed as another replacement for silk and quickly gained popularity for its strength, elasticity, and resistance to mildew with fewer of the flammability issues that plagued Rayon. The onset of World War II saw nylon in high demand for military applications, including parachutes and ropes.

Following the success of nylon, the fashion industry witnessed the introduction of several other synthetic fibres, including polyester in the 1950s. Developed from coal, air, water, and petroleum, polyester provided durability and wrinkle resistance, making it ideal for everyday wear. Its introduction marked the beginning of a new era in fashion, characterized by versatility and ease of care.

The 1960s and 70s saw a further expansion of synthetic materials with the introduction of acrylic, spandex, and improvements on rayon. Each of these fibres brought unique attributes to the fashion world, allowing designers to experiment with styles, colours, and silhouettes in unprecedented ways. As a result, the fusion of aesthetic appeal and functional practicality became a hallmark of modern fashion.

2.3 The Impact on Fashion Trends

Synthetic fibres have profoundly influenced fashion trends by enabling designers to push the boundaries of creativity. The affordability and availability of these materials allowed for mass production, making fashionable clothing accessible to a broader audience. As a result, fashion became less about social status and more about personal expression.

The vibrant colours and unique textures of synthetic fabrics encouraged the emergence of bold trends. For instance, the psychedelic prints of the 1960s and the disco-

inspired styles of the 1970s thrived on the use of polyester and spandex, which could be produced in various prints and styles. Furthermore, the development of stretch fabrics led to the popularization of form-fitting designs, significantly changing women's fashion and swimwear.

2.4 Sustainability and Controversy

Despite their benefits, the rise of synthetic fibres has not been without controversy, particularly to sustainability. The production of synthetic materials is resource-intensive, relying heavily on fossil fuels, and their non-biodegradable nature poses significant environmental challenges. The fashion industry has come under scrutiny for its contribution to pollution and waste, particularly with the rise of fast fashion, which prioritizes speed and low costs over ethical production. This is exacerbated by a Petrochemical Industry in decline and unethical industry lobbying of governments prevails to maintain legacy dominance. [6]

In recent years, consumers have become increasingly aware of these issues, prompting a demand for more sustainable practices. As a response, many brands have begun exploring alternatives to traditional synthetic fibres, including recycled polyester from plastic bottles and the development of biodegradable options. This shift reflects a growing recognition that the fashion industry must adapt to meet environmental challenges while still satisfying consumer demand for innovation and style.

The fast fashion phenomenon, characterized by rapid production cycles and low-cost garments, has further exacerbated these issues. Designers must navigate this landscape by prioritizing sustainability, exploring eco-friendly alternatives, and promoting ethical production practices that resonate with increasingly conscious consumers.

2.5 The Evolution of Consumer Behaviour

The interactions between synthetic fibres and consumer behaviour have also evolved. The affordability of synthetic fabrics has contributed to fast fashion's rise, wherein retailers can quickly produce and distribute the latest trends. This phenomenon has significantly altered shopping habits, leading to an increase in impulse buying and a culture focused on quantity over quality.

However, as the consequences of fast fashion become more apparent, consumers are increasingly valuing sustainability and ethical production. The emergence of the conscious consumer - someone who favours brands that prioritize eco-friendliness and fair labour practices - marks a shift in the market. Brands are now responding by emphasizing transparency in their sourcing and production processes and creating collections that utilize sustainable biosynthetic fibres.

3 Past Frameworks

Humanity has always sought sustainable ways to exist, from hunter-gatherer familial tribes co-existing alongside neighbouring tribes to collective agrarian urban living the need to sustain ourselves has been the underpinning driver in our survival as a species. Salas-Zapata, Ortiz-Munoz 2018 [9] noted the “ambiguity and polysemy” of the concept of sustainability, this concept warps even further when applied to the world of design of things in commercial manufacture.

As with Maslovs Hierarchy of needs from the physiological to safety and security needs, our ancestors have walked from Africa to Chile; from love and belonging to needs of self-esteem these attributes have formed many of the good and conversely more challenging behaviours, we should ask ourselves as the ultimate need, according to Maslov, what are the moral responsibilities of self-actualisation in sustainability?

We hear of the term “third world” being used by potential world leaders, identifying the difficulties in communicating concepts of civic enlightenment. A more able governance sees the use of the term developing countries rather than the arcane third world. As development continues and more populous nations strive for sustainability, we create pressures on the environment like never before experienced, vexing developing nations as international pressures demand sustainable performance across those societies to trade in the world of commerce.

Acknowledging the disparity of past practice in developed nations, in supply of goods to an international market, demands are being placed not only on the manufacture of those goods but the morality of commerce in elevating the standard of living, locally.

3.1 Societal Role

In this international order of globalisation, the international community has sought to not only develop standards but to set goals and targets to maintain a sustainable environment for the planet’s population through the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, identifying 17 goals and a number of targets to be achieved by the year 2030. Combined with international standards and codes, it is a daunting task for developing nations to comply with global wishes while having observed abuses of these same global goals by developed nations over the past millennia.

The moral responsibility within society whether developed or developing is to its constituents beyond borders, that of humanity and the natural world, as expressed by legal movements in the Rights of Nature in Law [10]. A beyond human-centered movement in design and sustainability is a response to this lack of diligence in meeting planet over profit.

Leadership is evident through the One UNEP (United Nations Environmental Programme). [11] They state that “The One UNEP Textile Initiative provides strategic leadership and encourages sector-wide collaboration to accelerate a just transition towards a sustainable and circular textile value chain. It has outlined the imperative for

the fashion sector to become radically and rapidly transformed to become circular and encapsulates and aligns all UNEP work on textiles to do so.”

Fig. 2. The One UNEP infographic

Under this UNEP umbrella is a focus of interest in the Indian textile market with Intex India [12] jointly funded through the Ministry of Environment of Denmark and the Indian Ministry of Textiles. Titled ‘Accelerating the Transition of the Indian Textile Sector towards Circularity’ to coordinate and align on circular textiles. Suggesting business assistance in “tools and guidelines that can help make your business more sustainable, circular and resilient”.

Active access to this programme by design and academic researchers can benefit the inclusive adaptation of best practice in the Indian context.

3.2 Designers Role

The designer’s role in sustainability is to regard these restrictions, moving practice beyond simple stylisation into a holistic process and strategy, positioning not only product but systems services and experiences in meeting the international market’s needs.

Design professional bodies such as the World Design Organisation predominantly covering the Industrial Design profession has acknowledged the expanding role of the designer from simply designing product, to systems, services and experience. Their stated interpretation of sustainability [13] quotes a number of sources, one being [14] Mollenkamp 2023 who state “focuses on meeting the needs of the present without com-

promising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. The concept of sustainability is composed of three pillars: economic, environmental, and social—also known informally as profits, planet, and people”.

Design gets blurred across disciplines from Artists and Craftspeople, the Arts & Crafts being small-scale production whereby Design as a profession is positioned at delivery of product at scale. This brings a higher degree of accountability to design within parameters established or being established by societies to protect the world from environmental catastrophe, indeed to view the natural world as a legal entity with rights.

3.3 Management’s Role

As organisations grow within the developing nations, so too does the responsibility of management to work within these parameters in facilitating the designer’s freedom to create and innovate and promote sustainable strategies expressing the desires of the international market.

According to McKinsey [15] a fourth dimension can be added to the triple bottom line, that of culture or to remain in keeping with the mnemonic P, Purpose is the link to social license, a growing principle to ESG Environment, Sustainability & Governance.

The predominance of startup companies and organisations attracted to the B Corp brand of ethical trading, practice or production is evidence of this push for purpose as an attribute in service delivery differentiation. According to the B Corp website [16] the certification programme has 9,313 members in 105 Countries across 106 industries employing 882,020 workers though membership in developing nations has been placed on hold which includes India and approximately 60 other countries.

This ‘hold’ could imply that the desire for a B Corp branding doesn’t reflect good ESG standards, and a lack of knowledge necessary for developing countries to build, as a catch-up, in compliance to trade internationally.

All too often designers experience qualified and unqualified pushback on these standards and are met with challenging situations and decisions beyond their control or capabilities as mere departments within corporate siloes.

While circularity and recycling provide a key design focus, attention has most recently been drawn to the scale and toxicity of microplastics entering the environment, and the human body. With the Petrochemical industry decline heading the same ways as coal with the move in mobility to electric over internal combustion [17] (IEEFA2024) leading to a reduction in fossil fuel consumption [18] and subsequently production, the feedstock of polymer filament production will be impacted.

Foresight in management practice and process is reflected through design maturity, the awareness of potential risks in material selection is a developing factor with “forever chemical” such as per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in non-stick cookware.

Fig. 3. BloombergNEF2024. Global Road Fuel Demand Peaks in 2027 [18]

3.4 Management and the Designer's role

Environmental Social Governance (ESG) has risen to prominence globally as the business strategy corollary established through International Standards Organisation's ISO9000 (Quality), 14001 (Environmental management) & ISO26000 (Social Responsibility) and leading to holistic approaches to business akin to the B Corp model of ethics in business.

Standards Australia the national body linked to the International Standards Organisation states that [19] "Environmental, Social & Governance (ESG) is the movement for businesses to operate in a transparent, environmentally and socially responsible way and to practice good governance. With a plethora of ESG disclosure standards, and the risk of greenwashing, organisations need guidance on how to effectively identify and implement their environmental, social and governance goals."

So, industry clearly is seeking to collaboratively navigate statutory requirements within their national boundaries and across international markets. Standards Australia continues "Whilst the popularity of ESG has been driven by customers and investors, ESG is also becoming increasingly important as a risk consideration for the long-term viability and success of an organisation."

A case in point is the Indonesian and Malaysian Governments' pushback [20] on environmental standards with the expansion of the Palm Oil Industry and deforestation. With the winding back of oil as a fuel within the fossil fuel industry, you could expect

impact on supply to the textile industry. Looking for more sustainable avenues in accessing oil has led to clearing of forests, so the hunt for arable land to produce hemp and other fibrous plant-based crops, has a bearing on the ecological footprint.

As nations have jockeyed for position on the globalisation scale of ‘ease of doing business’ as established by the World Bank, only to be halted [21] as Governments ‘gamed’ the system with skewed or fabricated statistics. The need for business ethics is evident though difficult to achieve.

3.5 Quadruple bottom line

The four p’s notion of Profit coming first, as has been the practice of the past, checked by environmental impact Planet concerns followed by societal implications People a fourth tranche has evolved of P for Purpose sometimes classified as culture, the latter two Ps are the sticking points of developing nations keen to gain a foothold in the international marketplace.

McKinsey [15] show an example of this four-quadrant structure through their consultancy work. Tom Shepard writes on outcomes of a “Design for Good” conference suggesting that the four P’s criteria are:

“It was during initial meetings for Design for Good, a new global non-profit alliance, when the team started to contemplate how project briefs could be improved. Here are four basic criteria we believe all creative briefs should consider:

Purpose: Why are we doing this at all, and are we in the best position to do it?

Profit: Does this project make financial sense with the technology and capabilities we have available?

People: Have we thought through the impact on people —not just the end users, but broader society as well?

Planet: How does this project leave our planet in a better place than before we started?”

McKinsey
& Company

Fig. 4. McKinsey - The four criteria of effective design

3.6 Innovation ladder

The Scandinavian Innovation ladder identified by Kretzschmar in 2003 [8] cleverly provides an introspective analysis of innovation within organisations and provides an informative structure upon which designs performance within organisations has currency. While non-designers strive for innovation in their practice, growing evidence of designs significance in value adding to that practice is mounting, with organisations such as McKinsey a staid and conservative consulting organisation embracing design within its practice and measuring its impact within leading organisations.

Process and Strategy are the designers 'glass ceiling' with few organisation /corporations with Chief Design Officer roles, meaningfully taking up the creativity and orig-

inality that design brings and the ethical responsibilities placed on the designers shoulders as they attempt to reflect societal needs within the products, systems services and experiences they are asked to envisage.

Manufacturing organisations understanding of designs role is emerging and is reflected in profit outcomes of enlightened organisations. Research through the Design management Institute has indicated that [22] Design Value Index 2015.

The move to placing designers within the corporate “C” Suite is a case in point of the elevation of significance beyond art and craft to that of business and needs to be given equal kudos within management.

3.7 Strategies for Sustainable Practice

Considering the pressing environmental issues associated with synthetic fibres, there are several strategies that designers can adopt to promote sustainability within their practices:

1. **Material Innovation:** Engaging in research on sustainable synthetic options, such as recycled polyester or bio-based fibres, can reduce reliance on virgin materials while maintaining desirable performance characteristics.
2. **Design for Longevity:** Emphasizing timeless design that transcends seasonal trends encourages consumers to invest in quality garments, thereby mitigating the impacts of fast fashion.
3. **Ethical Production:** Collaborating with local artisans and sustainable supply chains can enhance the cultural narrative of Indian fashion and contribute to positive social impacts within communities.
4. **Consumer Education:** Cultivating consumer awareness regarding the environmental impacts of fashion can drive a shift towards more responsible shopping habits, fostering a culture of sustainability.

The evolution of synthetic fibres has significantly shaped the fashion industry, particularly in India, where traditional craftsmanship intersects with modern synthetic materials. By understanding the historical context and implications of these fibres, designers can leverage their properties to create innovative and sustainable fashion.

Moving forward, the challenge lies in balancing the creativity of design with the imperative of environmental responsibility. This dual focus will be essential for the future success of the fashion industry amidst growing global sustainability concerns. As designers rise to this challenge, the integration of synthetic fibres with ethical practices will likely yield both aesthetic and ecological rewards through sourcing new materials to substitute for petrochemical staples.

4 Case Studies

Three scenarios are posed with these case studies or exemplars in behavioural change, best practice and development.

4.1 Wear Wool not Fossil Fuel /Waste

The Wool Mark Company [23] 2022 and again in [24] 2024 sought attention as a marketing strategy hoping to sway the public away from blended or synthetic fabrics, hoping that market forces would sway manufacturing to fall in line. The petrochemical industry has a dwindling hold on commerce as major programmes leverage the market to shift to renewables, but they will continue to produce synthetics in a rarified environment as drilling for oil becomes less viable through volume reduction.

Sustainability in the Australian and New Zealand sense is contentious with producers operating in conservative business environments and oscillating with intent, subject to political persuasion and rule.

The Australian Wool Innovation group's recent Sustainability report [25] largely focusses on land and animal management issues with small efforts in researching the natural fibre in the circular economy, while citing wool as “a circular fibre of the future”. No doubt this glossy document filled with heavily curated imagery of people working on the land, will have its effect, showing that sustainability is being considered, but reflects the underfunding of material science research in support of this industry.

4.2 H & M

H & M is a global fashion and design company with a reputation in the industry as leader in sustainability, their Sustainability Report [26] from 2023 states that “Our goal is to meet and exceed the expectations of our wide-ranging stakeholders alongside aligning with external reporting standards.” and links its action in terms of chemicals to the (AFIRM) group [27] who’s Vision and Purpose statements are as follows:

“Our Vision:

AFIRM continues to be a recognized global centre of excellence, providing resources to enable continuous advancement of chemical management best practices. We do this based on transparency, science, and collaboration with relevant industries and experts to build safer and more sustainable chemistry within the apparel and footwear supply chains.

Our Purpose:

To provide a forum to advance the global management of restricted substances in apparel and footwear, communicate information about RSL to the supply chain, discuss concerns, and exchange ideas for improving RSL management.”

The report references UNEP Eco-innovation efforts with a particular guideline for management in the textile industry. [28]

4.3 Sustineri

The United Nations Development Programme through the initiative of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) has set goals and targets as guidance for responsible manufacture and has a focus on the textile industry globally. The SDG 12 [29] covers sustainable production and consumption and sets targets for example 12.6 seeks to “encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices and sustainability reporting.”

The UNDP recently supported research in Fashion and Textiles in Asia through the Sustineri project [7] hosted through Hong Kong, the report focussed on six main areas: Carbon Targets, Energy Technologies, Sustainable Materials, Water Management, Pollution Control and Waste Reduction, with the aim to provide references to SMEs.

On sustainable materials the report states that “Increasing the percentage of organic materials and recycled materials used in production has become a most direct approach for many sustainable fashion brands. Crystal International Group, Hop Lun,²² and PVH²³ Corporation have used a larger portion of materials that meet or are certified to sustainability standards. Some of the commonly used standards include Better Cotton Initiatives (“BCI”), Global Organic Textile Standard (“GOTS”), Global Recycle Standard (“GRS”), Organic Content Standard (“OCS”), STANDARD 100 by Oeko-Tex[®], Recycled Claim Standard (“RCS”), Forest Certification (“PEFC”), Forest Stewardship Council (“FSC”), and Controlled Wood Mix.” And follows with biotech information on “organic” approaches with wood fibres on concern of petrochemical impracticability in recycling.

Fig. 5. Sustineri survey findings 2023

5 Conclusion

On the back of international standard design education in India over the past century, and Government initiatives like the “Make in India” campaign, the recent statement from Government on “Design in India, Design for the World” [30] sets the tone for real progress on building the framework for designers to impact industrial practices in sustainability, and the textile industry is well placed to reap the rewards.

According to the United Nations Fashion and Lifestyle Network [29] “Recognizing the fashion and lifestyle industries’ profound environmental, economic, and societal influence, the UN Fashion and Lifestyle Network actively advocates for transparent, inclusive, and transformative engagement among global stakeholders. The Network enables collaboration among industries and the UN system and accelerates innovation, knowledge sharing, and promotes members who are driving a positive impact on the Goals”. Emphasising the global realisation of the impact that the clothing and textile industries have on the environment and welfare and the need for concerted efforts to turn the industry around.

With global pressure on the reduction of fossil fuels the petrochemical industries need to be progressive in transition from synthetics towards biodegradable materials in an effort to stem the flow of microfibres into the atmosphere and into humans.

This in turn needs remedies in terms of agriculture and forest conservation as demand shifts to create larger land area available to cropping in fibre producing plants.

Ethical practice requires developed nations to respond empathically to developing nations abilities to transform practices from a feudal autocratic style of management to a more egalitarian and democratic organisational structure and allow designers the creative space to practice their profession and contribute meaningfully to production to meet global demands.

With the SDG target 12.9 [5] looking to “Support developing countries’ scientific and technological capacity for sustainable consumption and production: Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production” there is a need for Industry be it the Design Industry or the Manufacturing sector to develop quality frameworks that provide the tools and processes to make decision making accountable for those actions.

5.1 Looking to the Future

As the fashion industry continues to evolve, synthetic fibres will undoubtedly play a critical role. Innovations in textile technology suggest that the future of synthetic materials may be increasingly focused on sustainability. Bioengineering and advancements in textile recycling are likely to lead to the development of new, eco-friendly synthetic fibres that maintain the desirable properties of traditional materials while minimizing environmental impact.

The CFDA (Council of Fashion Designers of America) Innovation Index [31] is a valuable free resource of existing and emerging synthetic fibres that address the issues of sustainability, microplastics and recyclability.

Moreover, the integration of technology into textiles, such as smart fabrics that can monitor health or optimize comfort, could redefine how consumers interact with clothing. These innovations not only present unique design opportunities but also push the boundaries of what fashion can achieve in terms of functionality and experience.

Currently a staple in wardrobes around the world, synthetic fibres have transformed the way we perceive and engage with clothing. The challenge moving forward lies in balancing innovation with sustainability, ensuring that the future of fashion remains vibrant and responsible.

As the fashion industry continues to adapt to the demands of modern consumers, the legacy of synthetic fibres will undoubtedly shape its trajectory, highlighting the need for informed designers with agency to effect the significant changes needed to attain sustainability goals.

6 Recommendations

As India looks to build on its strengths in textile production as a global player in fashion, construction, manufacture including all markets and fields, the nation is well placed to be an exemplar in sustainability. The designer's place in that story is secure but in need of support.

There is an opportunity for the Association of Designers of India to engage with Intex India [12] and respective agencies to develop documentation and guidelines or practice notes to assist in specification documentation ensuring the product stays true to the design intent that is backed by research in World's best practice and statutory policy.

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